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EDITORIAL DESK

I wish to express my profound gratitude to Almighty God for the grace to successfully complete the volume 2 of the West African Journal of Educational Administration and Planning (WAJEAP).

The twelve articles were the products of well researched papers that were presented at the international conference held in May 2024 at the Presbyterian University of East Africa in Kikuyu, Nairobi, Kenya. The conference was well attended by over 25 universities across the globe. These published articles have been peer reviewed and plagiarism checks conducted on them before publication.

I, therefore, want to deeply appreciate the management team of the Presbyterian University of East Africa for making this publication a reality. All the writers and authors are congratulated for passing the stringent measures set by the guild of editors.

Congratulations to everyone.

Prof. M. O. B. Mohammed FNAEAP

Head, Editorial Team

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IMPACT OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY INNOVATIONS IN SOCIAL STUDIES EDUCATION AND ITS ATTENDANT'S IMPLICATIONS ON PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS IN LAGOS STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study looked into the impact of information and communication technology innovations in social studies education and its attendant's implications on primary school pupils in Lagos State. The implications of Information and Communication Technology innovation on primary school pupils in Lagos State are varied and far-reaching. With the advent of modern technology, the way pupils learn and engage with information has drastically changed in the field of social studies education, this change has been particularly significant. Descriptive survey research design was employed for the study. Population of the study was primary school teachers in Lagos State. One research instrument was used for the study titled 'Information and Communication Technology Innovation for Social Studies Teachers Questionnaire (ICTISSTQ). The instrument was validated by two experts in the department of Early Childhood Care & Primary Education of the Lagos State University of Education Oto/Ijanikin Lagos. Cronbach Alpha technique was used to check the internal consistency of the instrument that yield the index of $r = 0.82$. The findings of the study showed that there is a significant difference between male and female teachers on the use of computer tools in the classrooms. Also, there is a significant difference between teacher's computer related tools usage in the classroom and self perceptions of efficacy. It is therefore recommended that, the use of ICT should be extended to the teaching and learning process. Lastly, there is a need for a consistent electricity supply within the school environs.

Keywords: Teachers, Curriculum, ICT, Social Studies Education, Technology Innovations

INTRODUCTION

In recent time, the use of information and communication technology (ICT) has increasingly gained ground in education sector the world over. There has also been an increasing advocacy by educators, education counselors and education planners for the use of information and communication technology (ICT) in schools in Nigeria. This is so because the utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been considered as an effective medium in contributing towards the advancement of education (Arinze, Okonkwo & Iwunor, 2012). It is now a common scene to observe students browsing internet for materials for their assignment, lectures, and research study. It is because of the indispensable role of information and communication technology that made Oketunyi (2002) notes that use of ICT in Nigeria universities has become increasingly popular in that most universities now have electronic

libraries, and more students and lectures have varying forms of computer hardware and devices to search the web for the education resources.

According to UNESCO (2011), "ICT is a scientific, technological and engineering discipline and management technique used in handling information, its application and association with social, economic Information and Communication Technology (ICT) means involvement in the classroom. More specifically ICT can be defined as the use of all conceivable digital media in managing and processing information. Information is power. "No more swords to be feared than the learned pen". The phrase is so old that its origin cannot be traced. With knowledge come learning, skills, adaptability, understanding and activism-all factors that contribute to the growth of an equitable society. ICT offers the means to acquire this power. Since knowledge is vital, it follows that the acquisition of knowledge must be life-long.

ICTs are making dynamic changes in society. They are influencing all aspects of life. The influences are felt more and more at schools. Because ICTs provide both, pupils and teachers with more opportunities in adapting learning and teaching to individual needs, society is forcing schools aptly respond to this technical innovation. The role of ICT has become significant in the process of language learning. Since teaching itself is an art, ICT can make this artistic process more significant. The teachers and educators have also acknowledged the changes taking place in the field of teaching (Aboluwarin, Oyedapo & Osayande, 2023).

The uses of ICT is making major differences in the learning of pupils and teaching approaches. Schools in the Western World invested a lot for ICT infrastructures over the last 20 years, and students use computers more often and for much larger range of applications (Volman, 2005). According to Plante and Beatle (2004); outline benefits of ICT to Primary School as follows:

- ICT allows teachers to broaden and enrich the curriculum;
- Overall, ICT enables the curriculum to be more challenging and enriching;
- ICT enables pupils to go beyond the prescribed curriculum, thereby facilitating an increased knowledge base.

According to Beuke-Amis and Chiware (2006), the use of ICTs in Nigeria and African countries generally is increasing and dramatically growing. However, while there is a great deal of knowledge about how ICTs are being used in developed countries, there is not much information on how ICTs are being introduced into schools in developing countries. Looking at the developing countries according to these authors, there is generally limited access time per month using ICTs by both the teachers and students, and even less time spent with reliable Internet access. It should be noted that availability of ICTs vis-à-vis access in term of ratio of teachers and pupils differs significantly. Technology is supposed to engage in effective and efficient assessment of learning. Modern technology offers a broad range of tools that might employed in the classroom to greatly improve learning, reshaping the teaching and learning process in the process. By measuring students' learning regarding their performance in the classroom, technology can assist teachers. ICT, or information and communication technology, is now frequently used in assessments to develop assessment activities for pupils (Odebowale and Oyedapo, 2022).

Despite this, the new and emerging technologies challenges the traditional process of teaching and learning, and the way education is managed. While information communication technology is an important area of study in its own right, it is having a major impact across all curriculum areas. Easy worldwide communication provides instant access to vast array of data, challenging assimilation and assessment skills (Fowowe, 2006). Rapid communication

plus increased access to ICTs in the home, at work, and in educational establishment, could mean that learning becomes a truly lifelong activity- an activity in which the pace of technological change forces constant evaluation of teaching process itself, several studies reveal that pupils using ICT facilities mostly show higher learning gains than those who do not use.

In a social interaction process among pupils and between the pupils and the teacher, pupils gather knowledge in an active manner. The teacher must not be too supportive, because this forces the pupils into a passive, receptive role. As the pupils show they can perform the respective task independently, the teacher's support gradually vanishes ('fading'). The gradual shift from teacher-centered learning to pupil-centered learning is time-consuming and requires skillful teachers (Robinson and Latchem, 2003).

Iding, Crosby and Speitel (2002) describe several roles teachers fill when they are helping children to learn in computer-enriched classrooms. Initially, they serve as instructors to children in the use of computers. Later, as children gain more experience, the teacher's role moves to that of a coach. By using computers themselves, teachers can also serve as models to children. Teachers must be critics of computer software, learning to select the best software to enhance children's development. Hannafin and Savenye (1993) point out that the teachers' role does not change simply by using the computer in the classroom: 'The change occurs only to the extent to which a shift of responsibility to the learners occurs. The more responsibility and freedom is given to the learners, the greater the shift in the teachers' role'.

ICT in Social Studies Education

There has been a strong emphasis in Turkey to integrate Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in schooling by the governments in the last decade (M.E.B., 2011). Authorities governing Nigeria education and scholars alike are emphasizing the importance of educating pupils with knowledge and skills for independent and meaningful learning. This aim will be achieved better with the integration of ICT into teaching and learning process. Along with implementing projects to integrate ICT into education, the philosophy that lies under school curricula has also shifted towards constructivism (M. E.B., 2006).

Constructivist approach provides support for the importance of pupil-centred learning environment which promotes meaningful learning processes (Anderson, 2008). Because of this emphasis, there is great attention paid generic skills as well as knowledge. Social studies curriculums are also developed with a constructivist approach. Curriculum developers' vision of constructivist social studies is that pupils will be able to make sense of him/her and the society at large when engaged in learning environments dealing with real life issues (M.E.B., 2006).

Social studies curriculums are developed with an interdisciplinary approach in Nigeria (M.E.B., 2006). That is, the knowledge produced by the scholars of social sciences that are regarded as the basis for social studies such as history, geography, economics, sociology and so on is integrated in the curriculum in a way that in one lesson teaching and learning activities might be involving the knowledge and/or methods of all the social sciences mentioned above (Safran, 2004). Thus, social studies education in Turkey not only covers a wide range of knowledge bases produced by social sciences but also methodological approaches employed by social sciences in terms of skills education (Ata, 2012).

The subject of social studies is about real life for the real world. Pupils have experiences in real life. They bring those experiences into learning environments, and learning environments are affected by those experiences. Thus, it is important to incorporate real life issues in dealing with social studies pupils. It is also true that pupils' learning is more lasting when they deal with real life situations (Yanpar, 2011). Social studies cover a learning area that deals with abstract issues. Those abstract issues are difficult for some young pupils with low cognitive development level. What is needed is to create learning environments that utilizes concrete materials and tools. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) have potential in this sense for social studies (Gulbahar & Guven, 2008; Yesiltas & Sonmez, 2009).

ICT has the potential to bring real life issues into classrooms in a way that was not possible before in a traditional classroom setting. The flexible nature of ICT and the internet especially provide pupils (and others) with the opportunities for research, interaction, cooperation and collaboration (Cole, 2000). Utilizing moving and still images, conducting life histories, carrying out social research through ICT might make social studies meaningful and enjoyable which is otherwise might be considered a dull subject by some pupils (Dawson *et al.*, 2000; Acun, 2012).

ICT has tools for teaching, learning, research, information and interaction for pupils and educators. ICT integration into education might also have some ramifications for social studies (Beck & Eno, 2012; Acun, 2012). Especially, its ability to bring visual images of real life experiences through movies, documentaries and still images has great potential for younger pupils (Voogt, 2008; Dede, 2008).

Thus, computer-based teaching of Social Studies in Nigerian primary schools will help to enhance the intellectual and creative potentials of the pupils. The active involvement of the pupils in the generation of their own knowledge in this process will certainly produce active rather than inert knowledge characteristic of the teacher-dominated pedagogy. Such pupils will be better equipped with vital skills of problem solving and productive living. ICT integration in schools is needed in order to accomplish many objectives and improve the quality of lessons in all subject areas, as well as, social studies. ICT increasingly pervades various aspects of our daily lives like work, business, teaching, learning, leisure and health. Since ICT leads all processes based on information, every individual in a society should become technology competent. Thus, all schools have to be equipped with the necessary ICT in order to provide the next generations with the needed tools and resources for access and use and to attain the expected skills.

However, the emphasis on information and communication technology innovation in social studies education and its attendant implications on primary school pupils become more urgent considering the prevailing teacher-dominated approach to schooling and teaching in Lagos State. Learning is largely passive and products of the schools are rated low in creativity, critical thinking and problem-solving, apparently, because the schools have failed to develop such skills in them through the integration of digital technologies into the curriculum implementation process. Although the developing countries including Nigeria have become aware of the invaluable role of technology in effective teaching and learning, they have not been able to make significant progress in improving education through this medium. They base the potency of ICT to improve education and ameliorate most of the ineffectiveness in the schooling process in Nigeria; it becomes necessary to investigate the use of educational technology by social studies teachers in the primary and schools. This study is therefore aimed

at finding out the proportion of social studies teachers who use ICT for teaching and the factors that are related to their use of educational technology.

Research Questions

1. What is the adequacy level of the various aspects of ICT availability for social studies teachers’ in primary schools?
2. What are the factors hindering social studies teachers’ confidence during ICT usage in the teaching and learning process?
3. What are the teachers’ perceptions on the use of ICT in the teaching and learning of Social Studies?

Hypotheses

- H₀1:** There is no significant difference between teachers gender and computer tools usage in the classroom.
- H₀2:** There is no significant difference between teachers’ computer related tools usage in the classroom and self-perceptions of efficacy.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design typed. This design type helps to gather, organize and analyze data gotten from a pool of respondents and generalize its outcome on the larger population. The population for this study comprised all the primary school teachers in Lagos State. The samples of the study were 187 participants. A multistage sampling procedure was used for the study. One research instrument was used for the study titled ‘Information and Communication Technology Innovation for Social Studies Teachers Questionnaire (ICTISSTQ)’. The instrument was validated by two experts in the department of Early Childhood Care & Primary Education of the Lagos State University of Education Oto/Ijanikin Lagos. Reliability of the instrument was done through the use of Cronbach Alpha technique and the coefficient value of $r = 0.82$. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistic of t-test at 0.05 level of significant.

FINDINGS

Research Question 1: What is the adequacy level of the various aspects of ICT availability for social studies teachers’ in primary schools?

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.D
1. Computer	135 (72.2)	39 (20.9)	5 (2.7)	8 (4.3)	3.61	0.74
2. Internet	4 (2.1)	4 (2.1)	49 (26.2)	130 (69.5)	3.63	0.63
3. Interactive board	28 (15.0)	36 (19.3)	83 (44.4)	40 (21.4)	2.09	1.16
4. Projector	12 (6.4)	12 (6.4)	87 (46.5)	76 (40.6)	3.27	0.84
5. Multimedia	44 (23.5)	95 (50.8)	36 (19.3)	12 (6.4)	2.91	0.28
6. Printer	60 (32.1)	89 (47.6)	30 (16.0)	8 (4.2)	3.07	0.80
7. Scanner	61 (32.6)	71 (38.0)	47 (25.1)	8 (4.2)	2.86	0.92
8. Educational Software	32	36	63	56	2.09	1.16

	(17.1) (19.3) (33.7) (29.9)					
9. Visual library	12 28 40 107	1.70	0.94			
	(6.4) (15.0) (21.4) (57.2)					

Table above depicts the availability of ICT facilities in primary schools. The results shows that ICT facilities like internet and projector are not readily available (mean =3.63 and 3.07). Computers, printers, multimedia and scanners are available for the teaching and learning process (mean=3.61, 3.08, 2.91 and 2.86. while the remaining ICT facilities were not available among others are; interactive board, educational software and visual library (mean= 2.09, 1.70). The implication of this result is that, even when teachers are trained and willing to use ICT in their teaching, they may be discouraged because of the availability level of the required ICTs.

Research Question 2: What are the factors hindering social studies teachers’ confidence during ICT usage in the teaching and learning process?

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.D
1. Inefficient time to prepare materials based on technology	130 (69.5)	49 (26.2)	4 (2.1)	4 (2.1)	3.63	0.63
2. Inefficiency of teachers’ technical knowledge to prepare materials based on technology	115 (61.5)	51 (27.3)	9 (4.8)	12 (6.4)	3.43	0.85
3. Shortage of computers used by teachers	63 (33.7)	56 (29.9)	32 (17.1)	36 (19.3)	2.78	1.11
4. Poor technical and physical infrastructure of learning environments.	42 (22.5)	99 (52.9)	38 (20.3)	8 (4.3)	2.93	0.77
5. Lack of interest of teachers in technology usage	30 (16.0)	8 (4.3)	60 (32.1)	89 (47.6)	3.07	0.80
Weighted mean = 3.16						

Table above affirms factors hindering social studies teachers’ confidence during ICT usage in the teaching and learning process. The details analysis shows that; inefficient time to prepare materials based on technology (mean= 3.63), inefficiency of teachers’ technical knowledge to prepare materials based on technology (mean= 3.43), lack of interest of teachers in technology usage (mean= 3.07). Poor technical and physical infrastructure of learning environment (mean= 2.93) and Shortage of computers used by teachers (mean= 2.78).

Research Question 3: What are the teachers’ perceptions on the use of ICT in the teaching and learning of Social Studies?

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.D
1. I use the computer to teach my students social studies in the classroom	34 (18.2)	20 (10.7)	63 (33.7)	70 (37.4)	2.59	0.90
2. I use the computer to keep records of my students offering social studies	159 (85.0)	16 (8.6)	18 (4.3)	4 (2.1)	3.76	0.62
3. I browse the Internet to get materials for teaching Social Studies	12 (6.4)	12 (6.4)	87 (46.5)	76 (40.6)	1.80	0.84

4. I can use a search engine such as Google	65	84	30	8	3.10	0.82		
	(34.8)	(44.9)	(16.0)	(4.3)				
5. I can set up a multimedia projector	66	58	47	16	2.72	0.93		
	(35.5)	(31.0)	(25.1)	(8.6)				
Weighted mean = 2.79								

Table above affirms teachers’ perception on the use of ICT in the teaching and learning of social studies. The detailed analysis shows that; majority of the teachers use the computer to keep records of the students offering social studies (mean= 3.76), some teachers use search engine such as Google to search for an information related to social studies (mean= 3.10), teacher also set up a multimedia projector (mean= 2.72). Teachers use the computer to teach their pupils in the social studies classroom (mean= 2.59) and only few teachers browse the Internet to get materials for teaching Social Studies (mean= 1.80).

Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant difference between teachers’ gender and computer tools usage in the classrooms.

Summary of t-test showing teacher’s gender and computer tools usage in the classroom

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	Std.D	t	df	sig.	Remark
Computer tools usage in the classrooms	Male	74	13.073	1.184	14.234	185	0.000	significant
	Female	113	6.565	2.778				

Table above shows that there is a significant difference between male and female teachers on the use of computer tools in the classrooms (t = 14.234; df = 185; P<0.05). This implies male teachers have higher mean score in their computer tools usage in the classrooms (male = 13.07) than female teachers (6.56). Therefore, the null hypothesis 1 is rejected.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between teachers’ computer related tools usage in the classroom and self-perceptions of efficacy.

Summary of t-test showing teacher’s computer related tools usage in the classroom and self perceptions of efficacy

Variables	N	Mean	Std.D	t	df	sig.	Remark
Computer related tools usage	54	16.93	2.052	11.284	185	0.000	significant
Self-perceptions of efficacy	133	8.241	3.368				

Table above shows that there is a significant difference between teacher’s computer related tools usage in the classroom and self perceptions of efficacy (t = 11.284; df = 185; P<0.05). This implies computer related tools usage have higher mean score (16.93) than self-perceptions of efficacy (8.24). Therefore, the hypothesis 2 is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results revealed that the availability of computing facilities and the actual level of use of teachers in teaching and learning process was quite below average. However, good number of social studies teachers admitted that computer is mostly available in their

schools for instructional aims than the projectors, multimedia, scanner, educational software while on the other hand, and all the respondents' claims that they do not have interactive board and visual library in their respective schools.

Some of the teachers who are versatile in the use of computers system reported that they find Microsoft word and Microsoft Excel relevant and resourceful, using ICT for analyzing and keeping records of their pupils while Microsoft power-point (making slide presentations) and Microsoft access (database management) are rarely used. This finding agrees with earlier position that; in recent years major steps were taken in many countries to supply schools with ICT infrastructure (Yanpar, 2011), in the hope that technology will support innovative pedagogies and improve the teaching and learning processes. However, one of the main difficulties concerning the diffusion of innovative ICT based practices in schools is finding ways to engage teachers and students in using the new technologies effectively (Yesiltas & Sonmez, 2009).

Moreover, findings from this study suggest that social studies teachers understand the benefits of ICT usage in education. Social studies teachers considered computers as a viable educational tool that has the potential to bring about different improvements to their schools, students, lesson note, and to enhance lesson delivery, more productive and effective as a teacher in the classrooms. The findings of the study indicated there is a non significant difference between computers related tools usage in the classroom and self perception of efficacy. In addition, the study revealed that there was a non significant difference between teacher's computers related tools usage in the classroom and level of expertise.

The minority of teachers acknowledged the importance of using ICT in their own teaching. The majority of teachers also reported a lack of confidence in applying ICT in their teaching. Based on these results, it was observed that most teachers were not computer literate, and those that were are not deep inclined having the knowledge, skills required for adequate using of ICT to teach the student in the classroom. Training course desired needed for the teachers is highly implode to be put in place for the teachers in order to enhance skills in pedagogical and technical use of the ICT-based learning, program components and an increased motivation for using ICT.

CONCLUSION

In light of the findings of the study, it can therefore be concluded that by integrating information and communication technology into secondary school curriculum, a fundamental shift in the way teacher teach, and students learn will be evolved. The challenges of carrying out classroom instruction and research become less stressful with the advent of information and communication technology (ICT). Social studies education is a multi-disciplinary and problem-solving subject which demands that varieties of methods, materials, and learning experiences are required in its teaching and learning. ICT provides several kinds of materials, methods, skills, learning experiences that are used to solve political, cultural, economic and environmental problems that surround man. Utilization of ICT in teaching and learning of Social studies can assist the teacher and learners to discover new concepts, learn from other people's view points, and experiences and understand that there are several solutions to a particular problem. The use of ICT can help to involve the learners in active participation, working at their own pace, become self-regulated, self-motivated and thus facilitate teaching and learning of the subject.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The use of ICT should be extended to the teaching and learning process. The necessary facilities and equipment required for teachers and pupils to engage in teaching and learning should be provided.
2. There is a need for a consistent electricity supply within the school environs. The school can connect electricity directly from the nearest generating substation to the school.
3. Primary schools should capitalize on learners' ICT competence, strengthen the pedagogical use of ICT, develop an open knowledge-sharing culture with external stakeholders, and exploit the potential of ICT as a catalyst for change and tool through which to fulfill educational goals.
4. Government should revisit the curriculum at primary schools level with a view to incorporating the use of computer and ICT assisted instruction in the teaching and learning process.
5. All stakeholders in the school system should be adequately equipped to utilize ICT for teaching and managing activities in the system.

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